

Ship-to-Shore Network Monitoring Stack

Installation Guide & Security Architecture
pScheduler Result Archiver with perfSONAR on FABRIC

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1 Overview

This document provides installation instructions and a security architecture review for the **Ship-to-Shore Network Performance Monitoring Stack** [1]. The stack automates perfSONAR [5] network performance testing between research vessels (ships) and shore-side infrastructure, archives results in TimescaleDB, and provides Grafana dashboards for visualization. A lightweight custom archiver [2] replaces the standard perfSONAR toolkit's OpenSearch/Logstash backend, reducing memory requirements from 4–8 GB to under 1 GB—making it suitable for edge devices such as Raspberry Pis deployed on smaller research vessels.

Part I

Installation Guide

2 System Architecture

The monitoring stack [1] consists of two deployment roles connected over one or more IP networks:

- **Shore VM** — archive server running the Result Archiver stack (TimescaleDB, Grafana, Archiver API, Nginx) with a **native perfSONAR Testpoint** installed directly on the host (via `perfsonar-install.sh`). The native testpoint acts as a passive pScheduler endpoint—it does not initiate any tests itself, but participates in tests scheduled by the ship (e.g., as the responder in throughput, latency, and traceroute measurements).
- **Ship VM** — edge node running its own Archiver stack *plus* a **Docker-based perfSONAR Testpoint** container. **All tests are initiated by the ship.** The ship's testpoint schedules and triggers every measurement cycle (latency, RTT, throughput, MTU, clock, trace) on a cron schedule. The shore never initiates tests toward the ship.
- **NMEA Listener** (*optional*) — a lightweight Docker container that captures NMEA 0183 navigation data broadcast via UDP from vessel instrumentation (GPS receiver, gyrocompass, motion reference unit). Parsed data (position, heading, roll, pitch, heave) is archived alongside perfSONAR results in the `nav_data` TimescaleDB table, enabling Grafana dashboards that correlate network performance with vessel motion.

Figure 1: Ship-to-shore deployment architecture. Both VMs run the custom archiver stack (TimescaleDB, Grafana, Archiver, Ngix). All tests are initiated by the ship's Docker-based Testpoint on a cron schedule; the shore's native Testpoint acts as a passive responder. Results are archived locally on the ship and remotely to the shore.

2.1 Data Flow

Figure 2: End-to-end data flow. All tests are initiated by the ship’s cron-triggered Testpoint. Results are archived locally on the ship *and* remotely to the shore via HTTPS. The shore Testpoint is a passive responder only.

2.2 Component Summary

Container	Port	Purpose
archiver-nginx	8443 → 443	TLS termination, reverse proxy, rate limiting
archiver	3500 (internal)	REST API — ingests pScheduler JSON, upserts to DB
grafana	3000 (internal)	Visualization dashboards
timescaledb	5432 (internal)	PostgreSQL 16 + TimescaleDB time-series storage
perfsonar-testpoint	host network	pScheduler test execution (Docker on ship, Native on shore)
nmea-listener	host network	NMEA 0183 UDP listener (optional, ship only)

Table 1: Docker containers and port assignments. Only port 8443 is exposed to the host. The nmea-listener is optional and only deployed on vessels with NMEA instrumentation.

2.3 Why a Custom Archiver Stack?

The standard perfSONAR toolkit [5] (`perfsonar-archive` backed by OpenSearch and Logstash) requires significant memory and CPU resources. This makes it impractical for edge devices such as Raspberry Pis deployed on research vessels.

The custom archiver stack addresses this with a purpose-built, lightweight alternative:

- **TimescaleDB** (PostgreSQL extension) replaces OpenSearch + Logstash, drastically reducing memory usage from 4–8 GB to under 1 GB.
- A **relational data model** with composite primary keys enables idempotent re-ingestion—duplicate submissions are upserted, not duplicated.
- **TimescaleDB native compression** (after 7 days) and configurable retention policies replace OpenSearch index lifecycle management.
- A thin **REST API** with bearer token authentication replaces the Logstash HTTP pipeline, minimizing per-request overhead.
- **Grafana** dashboards are provisioned automatically with lightweight datasource and dashboard configurations.

The result is a stack that runs comfortably on a Raspberry Pi or a 2-core / 4 GB VM while maintaining full compatibility with standard perfSONAR pScheduler [5] tools—tests run identically, only the archiving backend differs.

3 Prerequisites

3.1 Operating System

Ubuntu 20.04, 22.04, or 24.04 LTS (recommended). Rocky Linux 8 or 9 also supported.

3.2 Required Software

- **Docker Engine** \geq 20.10 with **Docker Compose v2**
- **Git**
- **Python** \geq 3.9
- `openssl`, `curl`, `sed`, `awk`

Note

The setup scripts install Docker automatically if it is not already present.

3.3 Hardware Requirements

Role	CPU Cores	RAM	Disk
Shore (archive server)	4+ (16 recommended)	4 GB+ (8 GB recommended)	50 GB+
Ship (edge testpoint)	2+ (4 recommended)	2 GB+ (4 GB recommended)	20 GB+

Table 2: Minimum and recommended hardware for each role.

3.4 TLS Certificates

You must provide TLS certificates **before** starting the stack. Place them in the `certs/` directory:

```
mkdir -p pscheduler-result-archiver/certs
cp /path/to/fullchain.pem pscheduler-result-archiver/certs/
cp /path/to/privkey.pem pscheduler-result-archiver/certs/
chmod 600 pscheduler-result-archiver/certs/privkey.pem
```

For testing, generate a self-signed certificate:

```
openssl req -x509 -nodes -days 365 -newkey rsa:2048 \
-keyout pscheduler-result-archiver/certs/privkey.pem \
-out pscheduler-result-archiver/certs/fullchain.pem \
-subj "/CN=localhost"
```

Security Consideration

Self-signed certificates should only be used for testing. In production, use certificates issued by a trusted CA (e.g., Let's Encrypt).

4 Shore VM Installation

The shore node runs the Result Archiver stack and installs a **native perfSONAR Testpoint** directly on the host. The shore does not initiate any tests—it acts as a **passive pScheduler endpoint** so that the ship can schedule and execute measurements (throughput, latency, traceroute, etc.) against it.

4.1 Step 1: Clone the Repository

```
git clone https://github.com/kthare10/fabric-recipes.git
```

The setup scripts and deployment notebooks are maintained in the `fabric-recipes` repository [4].

4.2 Step 2: Generate a Bearer Token

```
export TOKEN=$(openssl rand -hex 32)
echo "Save this token: $TOKEN"
```

Note

This token is shared between the shore and ship nodes. Both sides must use the same token for authenticated archiver communication. Store it securely.

4.3 Step 3: Run the Setup Script

```
./fabric-recipes/perfsonar/node_tools/setup_shore.sh --token "$TOKEN"
```

Run this script twice. The first run installs Docker and adds your user to the `docker` group. You must log out and back in (or start a new shell) for group membership to take effect, then run the script again:

```
# After logging out and back in:
./fabric-recipes/perfsonar/node_tools/setup_shore.sh --token "$TOKEN"
```

4.4 What the Script Does

1. Clones `pscheduler-result-archiver` [2] from GitHub.
2. Runs `scripts/enable_docker.sh` — installs Docker, enables the service, adds the current user to the `docker` group, tunes kernel network parameters.
3. Runs `scripts/perfsonar-install.sh` — installs the **perfSONAR Testpoint** [5] natively on the host (pScheduler, OWAMP, iperf3, etc.), enabling the shore to act as a *passive* measurement endpoint for tests initiated by the ship.
4. Updates `archiver/config.yml` with the provided bearer token.
5. Generates a `.env` file with:
 - `ARCHIVER_DB_PASSWORD` — randomly generated (16-byte hex).
 - `ARCHIVER_BEARER_TOKEN` — the token you provided.
 - `GRAFANA_ADMIN_USER` / `GRAFANA_ADMIN_PASSWORD` — defaults to `admin/perfsonar`.
6. Launches the Docker Compose stack (`timescaledb`, `grafana`, `archiver`, `archiver-nginx`).

4.5 Step 4: Verify the Deployment

```
# Check all containers are running
docker ps

# Test the health endpoint
curl -sk https://localhost:8443/ps/health

# Test authenticated API access
curl -sk -H "Authorization: Bearer $TOKEN" \
  https://localhost:8443/ps/measurements/latency

# Verify Grafana is accessible
curl -sk -o /dev/null -w '%{http_code}' https://localhost:8443/
# Expected: 200 or 302
```

4.6 Step 5: Configure Grafana

1. Open `https://<shore-ip>:8443` in a browser (or via SSH tunnel to `https://127.0.0.1:8443`).
2. Log in with `admin` / `perfsonar` — change the password on first login.
3. Navigate to **Data Sources** → **perfsonar-postgres**.
4. Under **Authentication**, enter the database password (from `.env`).
5. Click **Save & Test** — confirm “Database Connection OK.”

6. Navigate to Dashboards → pScheduler → pscheduler-result-archiver (Pairs).

Figure 3: Grafana dashboard showing throughput, retransmits, latency, and RTT panels from the pScheduler Result Archiver. Data is read from TimescaleDB and displayed per source–destination pair.

5 Ship VM Installation

The ship node runs both the Archiver stack (for local archiving) and a perfSONAR Testpoint container that executes periodic network tests.

5.1 Step 1: Clone the Repository

```
git clone https://github.com/kthare10/fabric-recipes.git
```

5.2 Step 2: Define Test Targets and Archive URLs

The `HOSTS` variable tells the ship’s testpoint which **shore** endpoints to test against. The IP address is always the **shore’s IP**. Several formats are supported:

HOSTS format and examples (IP is always the shore IP)

```
# Format: <shore_ip>@<friendly_name>
# Alternative separators: name@ip, ip,name, ip|name, or just ip

# Example 1: Single shore host, single NIC
# 23.134.232.50 = shore IP
HOSTS="23.134.232.50@shore-STAR"

# Example 2: Multi-NIC --bind each test to a specific ship source interface
# Format: <shore_ip>@name%<ship_src_ip_or_iface>
# 23.134.232.50 = shore IP; eth1, eth2 = ship interfaces
HOSTS="23.134.232.50@shore-via-net1%eth1 23.134.232.50@shore-via-net2%eth2"
```

```
# Example 3: Multi-NIC with explicit ship source IPs instead of interfaces
# 23.134.232.50 = shore IP
# 10.135.145.2, 10.135.146.2 = ship source IPs on different networks
HOSTS="23.134.232.50@shore-net1%10.135.145.2 23.134.232.50@shore-net2%10.135.146.2"
```

Note

The % separator binds each test to a specific source interface. When an interface name is given (e.g., `eth1`), its IP is resolved at runtime, making the configuration resilient to DHCP renewals. This is essential for multi-NIC ship deployments where each NIC connects to a different network.

The `URLS` variable specifies where test results are archived. Multiple URLs are comma-separated. Remote URLs use the **shore's IP**:

Archive URL examples (remote URL uses shore IP)

```
# Local only (no remote archiving)
URLS="https://localhost:8443/ps"

# Local + remote shore archiver (recommended for redundancy)
# 23.134.232.50 = shore IP
URLS="https://localhost:8443/ps,https://23.134.232.50:8443/ps"

# Remote only (no local archiving)
# 23.134.232.50 = shore IP
URLS="https://23.134.232.50:8443/ps"
```

5.3 Step 3: Run the Setup Script

```
./fabric-recipes/perfsonar/node_tools/setup_ship.sh --token "$TOKEN" --hosts "$HOSTS" -
-urls "$URLS"
```

As with the shore setup, **run this script twice** (log out and back in between runs for Docker group membership).

5.4 What the Script Does

In addition to the shore steps (archiver stack), the ship setup also:

1. Clones `perfsonar-extensions` [3] from GitHub.
2. Creates the testpoint `.env` with host definitions, archive URLs, bearer token, and cron expression.
3. Launches the `perfsonar-testpoint` container (`docker-compose-testpoint.yml`).
4. Waits for the testpoint container to become healthy.

5.5 Step 4: Verify the Deployment

```
# All containers (archiver stack + testpoint)
docker ps

# pScheduler connectivity to shore
docker exec perfsonar-testpoint pscheduler ping <shore_ip>

# Verify cron schedule
docker exec perfsonar-testpoint crontab -l

# Check environment inside testpoint
docker exec perfsonar-testpoint printenv HOSTS
docker exec perfsonar-testpoint printenv ARCHIVE_URLS
```

5.6 Step 5: Run an Ad-Hoc Test

```
docker exec perfsonar-testpoint /usr/bin/python3 \
  /usr/src/app/periodic.py \
  --hosts "$HOSTS" \
  --output-dir /data \
  --archiver-urls "$URLS" \
  --auth-token "$TOKEN" \
  --reverse
```

6 NMEA Navigation Data Listener (Optional)

Research vessels such as the R/V Thompson broadcast NMEA 0183 navigation data via UDP. The **nmea-listener** container captures these broadcasts, parses them, and archives the data to the archiver REST API alongside perfSONAR network measurements. This enables Grafana dashboards that correlate network performance with vessel motion—for example, whether throughput drops when roll/pitch increases or when the vessel changes heading.

Note

The NMEA listener is **entirely optional**. It is only relevant for deployments on research vessels with NMEA 0183 instrumentation. Skip this section for land-based or non-vessel deployments.

6.1 Supported NMEA Sentences

Sentence	Source	Data Fields
\$INGGA	GPS receiver	Latitude, longitude, altitude, fix quality, satellites, HDOP
\$INHDT	Gyrocompass	True heading
\$PSXN,20	Kongsberg Seapath MRU	Quality/status indicators (horizontal, height, heading, roll/pitch)
\$PSXN,23	Kongsberg Seapath MRU	Roll, pitch, heading, heave

Table 3: NMEA 0183 sentences captured by the listener. Data from multiple sentence types received at the same timestamp are merged into a single `nav_data` row via COALESCE-based upsert.

6.2 Enabling the NMEA Listener

To deploy the NMEA listener, add the `--nmea-port` flag when running `setup_ship.sh`:

```
./setup_ship.sh --token "$TOKEN" --hosts "$HOSTS" --urls "$URLS" \
--nmea-port 13551 --vessel-id rv-thompson
```

The `--nmea-port` flag tells the setup script to:

1. Create an `.env` file for the listener with the specified port, bearer token, archive URLs, and vessel ID.
2. Build and launch the `nmea-listener` Docker container with host networking (required to receive UDP broadcast packets).

Omitting `--nmea-port` skips the NMEA listener entirely.

6.3 NMEA Listener Configuration

Variable	Default	Description
NMEA_UDP_PORT	13551	UDP port for NMEA broadcasts
ARCHIVE_URLS	<code>https://localhost:8443/ps</code>	Comma-separated archiver URLs
AUTH_TOKEN	(required)	Bearer token for archiver auth
VESSEL_ID	<code>rv-thompson</code>	Vessel identifier (partition key)
BATCH_SIZE	50	Points to buffer before flushing
FLUSH_INTERVAL_S	5.0	Max seconds between flushes
VERIFY_TLS	false	Verify TLS certificates
LOG_LEVEL	INFO	Logging verbosity

Table 4: NMEA listener environment variables (`nmea-listener/.env`).

6.4 Data Flow

1. **UDP reception** — The listener binds to `NMEA_UDP_PORT` with `SO_BROADCAST` and receives NMEA datagrams from vessel instrumentation.

2. **Parsing** — Standard sentences (\$INGGA, \$INHDT) are parsed with the `pynmea2` library. Proprietary \$PSXN sentences are parsed manually.
3. **Buffering** — Parsed data points accumulate in memory. A flush is triggered when the buffer reaches `BATCH_SIZE` or `FLUSH_INTERVAL_S` elapses.
4. **Archiving** — Batches are POSTed as JSON to `POST /ps/measurements/nav` on all configured `ARCHIVE_URLS` with bearer token authentication. This enables dual archiving to both the local (ship) and remote (shore) archivers.

6.5 Database Schema

Navigation data is stored in the `nav_data` TimescaleDB hypertable with a composite primary key (`ts`, `vessel_id`):

Column	Type	Description
<code>ts</code>	TIMESTAMPTZ	Measurement timestamp (PK)
<code>vessel_id</code>	VARCHAR(64)	Vessel identifier (PK)
<code>latitude</code>	FLOAT	Degrees (from GGA)
<code>longitude</code>	FLOAT	Degrees (from GGA)
<code>altitude_m</code>	FLOAT	Meters above sea level
<code>fix_quality</code>	INTEGER	GPS fix quality indicator
<code>num_satellites</code>	INTEGER	Satellites in view
<code>hdop</code>	FLOAT	Horizontal dilution of precision
<code>heading_true</code>	FLOAT	True heading in degrees (from HDT)
<code>motion_status</code>	INTEGER	MRU quality status (from PSXN,20)
<code>roll_deg</code>	FLOAT	Roll in degrees (from PSXN,23)
<code>pitch_deg</code>	FLOAT	Pitch in degrees (from PSXN,23)
<code>heave_m</code>	FLOAT	Heave in meters (from PSXN,23)
<code>aux</code>	JSONB	Additional raw data

Table 5: The `nav_data` table schema. Compression after 7 days and retention of 180 days are applied automatically via TimescaleDB policies.

6.6 Navigation Correlation Dashboard

The archiver stack includes a pre-provisioned **Navigation Correlation** Grafana dashboard with the following panels:

- **Vessel Position** — Geomap showing latitude/longitude track
- **Throughput vs. Roll/Pitch** — Dual Y-axis correlating network throughput with vessel motion
- **RTT vs. Heave** — Round-trip time correlated with heave
- **Heading & GPS Quality** — True heading, fix quality, and satellite count over time
- **Motion Detail** — Roll, pitch, and heave time series
- **Loss vs. Motion Severity** — Packet loss correlated with combined roll/pitch magnitude

The dashboard includes template variables for filtering by source/destination IP, traffic direction, and vessel ID.

6.7 Time-Aligned Environmental Correlation Dashboard

A second pre-provisioned dashboard, **Time-Aligned Environmental Correlation**, provides a stacked multi-panel view modeled after the correlation analysis in the R/V *Sikuliaq* study. All panels share a synchronized time axis and crosshair tooltip, enabling rapid visual identification of environmental events that coincide with network degradation.

- **Throughput (Upload / Download)** — iperf3 throughput split by traffic direction
- **Round-Trip Time** — RTT measured by ping and tcpping
- **Latency** — Average one-way latency (owping/halfping)
- **Heading** — True heading (10-min max aggregation)
- **Roll** — Vessel roll angle (10-min max absolute)
- **Pitch** — Vessel pitch angle (10-min max absolute)
- **Heave** — Vessel heave (10-min max absolute)

Roll, pitch, and heave values are downsampled to 10-minute intervals using maximum aggregation to reduce short-timescale noise while preserving peak vessel motion magnitudes. The default time range is 7 days.

7 Test Frequency

The perfSONAR Testpoint container runs tests on a cron schedule defined by the `CRON_EXPRESSION` variable in the testpoint `.env` file (`perfsonar-extensions/docker/.env`).

Default: every 6 hours at minute 0

```
CRON_EXPRESSION=0 */6 * * *
```

To change the test frequency, edit the `.env` file and restart the container:

```
# Edit the cron expression
cd perfsonar-extensions/docker
vi .env # change CRON_EXPRESSION

# Restart the testpoint (picks up new .env)
docker compose -f docker-compose-testpoint.yml up -d
```

Common schedules:

Expression	Frequency
0 */6 * * *	Every 6 hours (default)
0 */4 * * *	Every 4 hours
0 */2 * * *	Every 2 hours
0 * * * *	Every hour
*/30 * * * *	Every 30 minutes
0 3 * * *	Once daily at 03:00

Table 6: Common cron expressions for test scheduling.

Note

Each test cycle runs the full suite (latency, RTT, throughput, MTU, clock, trace) for every host in `HOSTS`. More frequent schedules increase network and CPU load on both endpoints. For satellite/constrained links, every 4–6 hours is recommended.

8 Enabling and Disabling Remote Archiving

By default, the ship archives results both **locally** and to the **remote shore archiver**. This is controlled by the `ARCHIVE_URLS` variable in the testpoint `.env` file.

8.1 Disable Remote Archiving (Local Only)

Set `ARCHIVE_URLS` to only the local endpoint:

```
# In perfsonar-extensions/docker/.env
ARCHIVE_URLS=https://localhost:8443/ps
```

8.2 Re-enable Remote Archiving

Add the shore archiver URL back (comma-separated):

```
ARCHIVE_URLS=https://localhost:8443/ps,https://23.134.232.50:8443/ps
```

After changing, restart the testpoint:

```
cd perfsonar-extensions/docker
docker compose -f docker-compose-testpoint.yml up -d
```

Note

Remote archiving requires that port 8443 on the shore VM is reachable from the ship, and that both sides share the same bearer token. If the remote archiver is temporarily unreachable, the testpoint will log errors but continue running tests and archiving locally. Results are **not** retried automatically—they must be re-submitted or the test re-run.

9 SSH Tunnel Access

If the shore or ship VM is not directly accessible on port 8443, use an SSH tunnel:

```
ssh -L 127.0.0.1:8443:127.0.0.1:8443 user@<vm-ip>
```

Then access Grafana at <https://127.0.0.1:8443>.

For multiple VMs, increment the local port:

```
# Shore
ssh -L 127.0.0.1:8443:127.0.0.1:8443 user@<shore-ip>
# Ship
ssh -L 127.0.0.1:8444:127.0.0.1:8443 user@<ship-ip>
```

10 Configuration Reference

Variable	Description
ARCHIVER_DB_PASSWORD	PostgreSQL password (auto-generated)
ARCHIVER_BEARER_TOKEN	API authentication token
GRAFANA_ADMIN_USER	Grafana admin username (default: <code>admin</code>)
GRAFANA_ADMIN_PASSWORD	Grafana admin password (default: <code>perfsonar</code>)
GRAFANA_DOMAIN	Grafana server domain (default: <code>127.0.0.1</code>)
GRAFANA_PORT	Grafana external port (default: <code>8443</code>)

Table 7: Archiver stack environment variables (`.env`).

Flag	Description
<code>--token</code> TOKEN	Bearer token for API authentication (required)
<code>--hosts</code> "... " (ship only)	Space-separated test targets with optional source binding
<code>--urls</code> URL,URL (ship only)	Comma-separated archiver endpoint URLs
<code>--workdir</code> PATH	Working directory (default: <code>\$PWD</code>)
<code>--archiver-repo</code> URL	Override archiver Git repository URL
<code>--archiver-branch</code> BRANCH	Override archiver Git branch
<code>--psx-repo</code> URL (ship only)	Override perfsonar-extensions repository URL
<code>--psx-branch</code> BRANCH (ship only)	Override perfsonar-extensions branch
<code>--nmea-port</code> PORT (ship only)	Enable NMEA listener on this UDP port (e.g., 13551). Omit to skip.
<code>--vessel-id</code> ID (ship only)	Vessel identifier for <code>nav_data</code> table (default: <code>rv-thompson</code>)
<code>--no-sudo</code>	Disable sudo (run as root directly)
<code>--verbose</code>	Enable debug output

Table 8: Setup script command-line options.

Metric	Test Tool
throughput_mbps, retransmits	iperf3
delay_ms, jitter_ms, loss_pct	owping / twping / halfping
rtt_ms (mean/min/max)	ping / tcpping
mtu_bytes	fwmtu
hop_count	tracert / tracepath
clock_diff_ms, clock_offset_s	psclock

Table 9: Supported test metrics collected and stored in TimescaleDB.

Part II

Security Architecture

11 Threat Model

The system operates in a scenario where:

- Ship and shore nodes communicate over potentially untrusted networks (research networks, satellite links, public internet) [7].
- The archiver API is exposed on port 8443 and must accept results from remote testpoints.
- Grafana dashboards are accessed by operators via SSH tunnels or direct HTTPS.
- Edge devices (ships) may be physically accessible to non-administrators.

Key assets to protect:

1. **Measurement data integrity** — results must not be tampered with.
2. **API authentication credentials** — bearer tokens must not be leaked.
3. **Dashboard access** — Grafana must require authentication.
4. **System availability** — the stack must resist denial-of-service.

12 Network Security

12.1 Port Exposure — Archiver Stack

The archiver stack exposes a single port to the host network. All other services communicate over the Docker bridge network:

Port	Service	Protocol	Binding	Notes
8443	NGINX	HTTPS	0.0.0.0	Only externally exposed port
3500	Archiver API	HTTP	Docker internal	Not reachable from host
3000	Grafana	HTTP	Docker internal	Proxied through NGINX
5432	TimescaleDB	PostgreSQL	Docker internal	Not exposed to host

Table 10: Archiver stack port exposure. Only port 8443 is reachable from outside the Docker network.

12.2 Port Exposure — perfSONAR Testpoint

All tests are initiated by the ship. The shore never schedules or triggers tests toward the ship. On the **shore** (native install), the ports in Table 11 must be open [6] to accept inbound connections from the ship. On the **ship** (Docker with host networking), the testpoint opens listener ports on the host but **no inbound perfSONAR traffic is expected**—all connections are initiated outbound by the ship. Even when using iperf3’s `--reverse` flag, the ship (client) initiates the TCP connection

to the shore’s port 5201; the flag only reverses the *data direction* over the already-established connection.

Port(s)	Proto	Service	Purpose	Inbound On
8443	TCP	NGINX (archiver)	TLS proxy, result archiving, Grafana	Shore + Ship
443	TCP	pScheduler API	Test scheduling and coordination	Shore only
861	TCP	OWAMP control	One-way latency control channel	Shore only
8760–9960	UDP	OWAMP test	One-way latency data (1200-port range)	Shore only
862	TCP	TWAMP control	Two-way latency control channel	Shore only
18760–19960	UDP	TWAMP test	Two-way latency data (1200-port range)	Shore only
5201	TCP/UDP	iperf3	Throughput testing	Shore only
33434–33634	UDP	Traceroute	Path tracing (200-port range)	Shore only
123	UDP	NTP	Clock synchronization	Shore only
ICMP	—	Ping	RTT and connectivity tests	Shore only

Table 11: Inbound port requirements by role. All perfSONAR measurement ports are inbound on shore only. The ship requires only 8443 (for operator Grafana access, typically via SSH tunnel) and no inbound perfSONAR ports.

Security Consideration

Shore VM: The perfSONAR Testpoint is installed *natively* on the host, so the ports above are opened directly on the host by the perfSONAR package installation.

Ship VM: The `perfsonar-testpoint` container runs with `network_mode: host` and `privileged: true`. This is required for pScheduler operation (systemd, raw sockets for OWAMP). A container compromise is equivalent to a host compromise. The testpoint container should only be deployed on dedicated measurement nodes. Although the container opens listener ports on the host, no inbound perfSONAR traffic is expected.

Note

This architecture is well-suited for ship deployments behind NAT or strict firewalls. The ship only needs outbound access to the shore’s perfSONAR and archiver ports. The `--reverse` flag in `iperf3` reverses the data direction *within* the existing TCP connection that the ship opened—it does **not** cause the shore to open a new connection back to the ship.

12.3 TLS Configuration

NGINX terminates TLS with the following settings:

nginx/default.conf (TLS)

```
ssl_protocols TLSv1.2 TLSv1.3;
ssl_certificate /etc/ssl/public.pem;
ssl_certificate_key /etc/ssl/private.pem;
```

- TLS 1.0 and 1.1 are **disabled**.
- HSTS is enforced with a 1-year max-age: `Strict-Transport-Security: max-age=31536000; includeSubDomains`.

- Internal traffic between containers uses plain HTTP over the Docker bridge network (acceptable since it never leaves the host).

12.4 Firewall Recommendations

The shore VM must have all perfSONAR ports open [6] because the ship connects to them for every test. The ship requires only SSH and the archiver port (8443)—no inbound perfSONAR ports are needed since all tests are initiated outbound by the ship.

Shore VM firewall rules

```
# SSH
ufw allow 22/tcp

# Archiver stack (NGINX TLS) --receives results from ship
ufw allow 8443/tcp

# pScheduler API --ship schedules tests via this port
ufw allow 443/tcp

# OWAMP (one-way latency)
ufw allow 861/tcp
ufw allow 8760:9960/udp

# TWAMP (two-way latency)
ufw allow 862/tcp
ufw allow 18760:19960/udp

# iperf3 (throughput)
ufw allow 5201/tcp
ufw allow 5201/udp

# Traceroute
ufw allow 33434:33634/udp

# NTP
ufw allow 123/udp

# Apply
ufw default deny incoming
ufw enable
```

Ship VM firewall rules

```
# SSH
ufw allow 22/tcp

# Archiver stack (NGINX TLS) --for operator dashboard access
ufw allow 8443/tcp

# No perfSONAR inbound ports needed --all tests are initiated
# outbound by the ship. Even --reverse iperf3 uses the existing
# outbound connection.
```

```
# Apply
ufw default deny incoming
ufw enable
```

Note

The shore **must** have all perfSONAR ports open since the ship connects to them for every test. The ship needs only SSH and the archiver port (8443) for operator access—no inbound perfSONAR ports are required.

13 Authentication & Authorization

13.1 Archiver API Authentication

The archiver API supports two authentication methods (either is sufficient):

1. **Bearer Token** — Authorization: Bearer <token>
2. **API Key** — X-API-Key: <token>

Both are validated against the ARCHIVER_BEARER_TOKEN environment variable. The token is a 64-character hex string generated with `openssl rand -hex 32`.

Endpoint	Method	Auth Required	Purpose
/ps/health	GET	No	Health check
/ps/measurements/*	POST	Yes	Ingest test results
/ps/measurements/nav	POST	Yes	Ingest NMEA navigation data
/ps/nav	GET	Yes	Retrieve navigation data
/ps/archives/*	GET	Yes	Retrieve archived results
/ps/ui	GET	No	Swagger UI (API documentation)
/ (Grafana)	GET	No	Grafana login page (has its own auth)

Table 12: API endpoints and authentication requirements.

13.2 Grafana Authentication

- Default credentials: `admin` / `perfsonar` (must be changed on first login).
- Session lifetime: 30 days (inactive and absolute).
- Token rotation interval: 24 hours.
- Cookie settings: `Secure=true`, `SameSite=Lax`.

13.3 Database Authentication

- Single user `grafana_writer` with a randomly generated password.
- SSL disabled for database connections (traffic is container-internal only).
- Connection pooling: 10 connections, 20 max overflow, 30s timeout.

14 Security Headers & Hardening

14.1 HTTP Security Headers

NGINX adds the following headers to all responses:

Header	Value
X-Frame-Options	DENY
X-Content-Type-Options	nosniff
X-XSS-Protection	1; mode=block
Strict-Transport-Security	max-age=31536000; includeSubDomains
Referrer-Policy	strict-origin-when-cross-origin

Table 13: Security headers applied by NGINX.

14.2 Rate Limiting

- API endpoints (/ps/*): 10 requests/second per client IP with burst allowance of 20.
- Grafana endpoints: no rate limiting (protected by session authentication).
- Request body size limit: 10 MB (`client_max_body_size`).

14.3 CORS Policy

The API handles CORS preflight requests with:

- `Access-Control-Allow-Origin`: * (permissive, for testpoint compatibility).
- `Access-Control-Allow-Credentials`: `true`.
- Allowed methods: GET, POST, PUT, PATCH, DELETE, OPTIONS.

Security Consideration

The wildcard CORS origin is intentionally permissive to support testpoints on diverse network addresses. If all testpoint IPs are known in advance, restrict the origin to specific addresses.

14.4 Container Isolation

Container	User	Privileged	Network	Notes
archiver	archiver (1000)	No	Bridge	Non-root, minimal filesystem access
grafana	472:0	No	Bridge	Standard Grafana UID
timescaledb	postgres	No	Bridge	Data volume mounted
archiver-nginx	root	No	Bridge	Requires root for port 443 binding
perfonar-testpoint	root	Yes	Host	Ship: Required for systemd/pScheduler; Shore: Native install, runs as system services
nmea-listener	nmea (1000)	No	Host	Non-root; host networking for UDP broadcast (optional)
perfonar-testpoint	root	N/A	Host	Native install on shore; runs as system services

Table 14: Container and service security posture.

15 Secrets Management

15.1 Secrets Inventory

Secret	Generation	Storage
ARCHIVER_BEARER_TOKEN	openssl rand -hex 32	.env file + config.yml
ARCHIVER_DB_PASSWORD	openssl rand -hex 16	.env file
GRAFANA_ADMIN_PASSWORD	User-provided or default	.env file
TLS private key	User-provided	certs/privkey.pem

Table 15: Secrets and their lifecycle.

15.2 Secret Lifecycle

- Bearer tokens are generated once during setup and do not expire.
- Database passwords are generated once and persist across container restarts (stored in Docker volumes).
- The .env file is **not** committed to version control (.gitignore).
- TLS certificates must be rotated manually or via external automation (e.g., certbot).

16 Data Security

16.1 Data Model

The database contains three primary tables:

- `ps_test_results` — Network measurement results with composite PK (`run_id`, `metric_name`, `ts`, `src_ip`, `dst_ip`, `direction`). Enables idempotent re-ingestion via upsert.
- `ps_trace_hops` — Traceroute hop-by-hop data with PK (`run_id`, `hop_idx`).
- `nav_data` — NMEA navigation data with composite PK (`ts`, `vessel_id`). Multiple NMEA sentence types received at the same timestamp are merged via COALESCE-based upsert.

16.2 Data Retention & Compression

- TimescaleDB native compression after **7 days**.
- Automatic data retention: **180 days** (configurable in `config.yml`).
- JSONB aux column stores raw pScheduler tool output for forensic analysis.

16.3 Backup Considerations

TimescaleDB data is stored in a Docker volume (`./tsdb_data`). Recommended backup approaches:

- `pg_dump` via `docker exec timescaledb pg_dump -U grafana_writer perfsonar`
- Volume-level snapshots if running on cloud infrastructure.
- Bidirectional archiving (`ship` → `shore` and `shore` → `ship`) provides built-in redundancy.

17 Known Risks & Mitigations

ID	Severity	Risk	Mitigation
R1	High	Privileged testpoint container. The <code>perfsonar-testpoint</code> runs with <code>privileged: true</code> and host networking. Container compromise equals host compromise.	Deploy testpoint only on dedicated measurement nodes. Restrict SSH access. Monitor container logs for anomalies.
R2	Medium	No bearer token expiry. API tokens never expire and cannot be revoked without restarting containers.	Rotate tokens periodically by updating <code>.env</code> and restarting the stack. Future: implement token expiry and revocation.

ID	Severity	Risk	Mitigation
R3	Medium	Permissive CORS. Wildcard origin (*) with credentials enabled could allow cross-origin credential leakage in browser contexts.	Restrict CORS origins to known testpoint IPs if browser-based access to the API is not required.
R4	Medium	TLS verification disabled in client. The <code>ArchiverClient</code> uses <code>verify=False</code> for self-signed certificates, making it vulnerable to MITM attacks.	Use CA-signed certificates in production and set <code>verify=True</code> . Distribute CA bundle to testpoint containers.
R5	Medium	Shared database user. Grafana and the archiver share the <code>grafana_writer</code> user with full write permissions.	Create a read-only PostgreSQL user for Grafana.
R6	Low	No audit logging. API requests are not logged with authentication context. Failed authentication attempts are not tracked.	Add structured logging for all authenticated requests. Integrate with fail2ban or similar for brute-force detection.
R7	Low	Rate limiting bypass. Per-IP rate limiting can be circumvented with IP rotation. No per-token throttling.	Acceptable for current deployment scale. Add per-token rate limiting if the API becomes publicly accessible.

18 Security Recommendations

18.1 Immediate Actions

1. Change the default Grafana password immediately after deployment.
2. Use CA-signed TLS certificates in production.
3. Restrict firewall rules to allow only necessary ports (8443, 22).
4. Verify that the `.env` file is not accessible to unauthorized users (`chmod 600 .env`).

18.2 Short-Term Improvements

5. Implement bearer token rotation with a defined lifecycle.
6. Create a read-only PostgreSQL user for Grafana.
7. Restrict CORS origins to known testpoint IP addresses.
8. Enable TLS verification (`verify=True`) in the archiver client.
9. Add structured audit logging for API requests.

10. Implement IP allowlisting at the NGINX level for known testpoint addresses.

18.3 Long-Term Enhancements

11. Integrate with a secrets manager (e.g., HashiCorp Vault) for credential lifecycle management.
12. Implement mutual TLS (mTLS) for testpoint-to-archiver communication.
13. Add role-based access control (RBAC) with scoped API tokens.
14. Enable PostgreSQL encryption at rest.
15. Conduct a third-party security audit.

19 File Reference

File	Purpose
<code>docker-compose.yml</code>	Orchestrates the 4-container archiver stack
<code>nginx/default.conf</code>	TLS termination, reverse proxy, rate limiting, security headers
<code>archiver/config.yml</code>	Archiver runtime configuration (DB, token, logging, retention)
Dockerfile	Archiver container image (Python 3.13, non-root user)
<code>certs/fullchain.pem</code>	TLS certificate chain (user-provided)
<code>certs/privkey.pem</code>	TLS private key (user-provided)
<code>.env</code>	Secrets file (not committed to version control)
<code>provisioning/datasources/</code>	Grafana datasource auto-provisioning
<code>provisioning/dashboards/</code>	Grafana dashboard auto-provisioning (Pairs + Nav Correlation)
<code>scripts/enable_docker.sh</code>	Docker installation and kernel tuning
<code>scripts/perfsonar-install.sh</code>	perfSONAR client package installation
<code>scripts/archiver_update_config.py</code>	Token injection into config.yml
<i>NMEA Listener (perfsonar-extensions/nmea-listener/)</i>	
<code>nmea.listener.py</code>	Main NMEA UDP listener and parser
<code>nmea.sim.py</code>	NMEA simulator for testing (no dependencies)
Dockerfile	Container image (Python 3.13-slim, non-root)
<code>docker-compose-nmea.yml</code>	Compose file (host networking)
<code>env.template</code>	Configuration template

20 Revision History

Date	Author	Changes
June 9, 2026	Komal Thareja	Initial document — installation guide and security review.

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